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INNOVATION FOR TOMORROW: PROGRESS IN SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE CONCEPTS

ABSTRACT BOOK

escalating to over 435 times more toxic in F5 (EC50_reproduction of >478 and 1.10 mg L⁻¹ for PFBS and FBSA, respectively), and also showed a higher bioaccumulation potential (BAF of 7.76 and 16.4 L kg⁻¹ for PFBS and FBSA, respectively). These findings highlight that the conventional single-generation ecotoxicity tests underestimate PFAS ecotoxicity during multigeneration exposure, and that the environmental risks of PFAS cannot reliably be assessed by the current limited subset of studied compounds. This research was supported by the Open Technology Programme of the Dutch Research Council (NWO) [grant number 18725]

1.01.T-03 Multigenerational Reproductive Toxicity of Arsenic in Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)

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Arsenic causes reproductive toxicity in animal models via endocrine disruption, however, whether the toxicity persists beyond one generation (F0) is largely unknown. Our study was designed to investigate whether the multigenerational reproductive effects of arsenic occur via maternal or paternal lineage and to gain insights into the potential underlying epigenetic mechanisms. Adult zebrafish (F0 generation) were exposed to environmentally relevant doses of arsenic via diet [0 (control), 30 (low), 60 (medium), and 100 (high) g/g dry weight, as arsenite] for 90 days. Following exposure, arsenic-treated females were crossed with control males, and vice versa, to assess the reproductive effects of sex-specific arsenic exposure. Arsenic exposure in females resulted in a dose-dependent decrease in fecundity and fertilization rate. In contrast, arsenic exposure in males induced similar reproductive effects predominantly at the high arsenic exposure dose. Subsequently, F1 generation larvae from different maternal and paternal arsenic treatments were raised to adulthood in clean water and diet, and males and females from the same treatment were then bred to evaluate the reproductive effects of maternal and paternal arsenic exposure. Maternal arsenic exposure decreased fecundity and fertilization success, even at the low dose, whereas the same reproductive effects were recorded only at medium and high doses with paternal arsenic exposure. In addition, the genes involved in the hypothalamus-pituitary gonad liver (HPGL) axis were consistently downregulated in F0 females directly exposed to arsenic as well as in F1 males and females maternally exposed to arsenic, irrespective of dose levels. On the other hand, the HPGL axis genes were downregulated in F0 males exposed directly to medium and high arsenic doses and in F1 generation males and females paternally exposed to the same arsenic doses. Furthermore, we also found that arsenic exposure led to hypermethylation of the promoter region of key HPGL axis genes, specifically steroidogenic factor-1 in the brain and *cyp19a1a* in the gonads in F0 and F1 males and females. This indicated that the downregulation of critical HPGL axis genes was mediated by arsenic-induced DNA hypermethylation. Overall, our study demonstrated that arsenic exposure causes multigenerational reproductive toxicity in zebrafish by disrupting the HPGL axis via epigenetic alterations, and these effects occur via both maternal and paternal lineages.

1.01.T-04 New Insights Into Cadmium Sub-Lethal Effects on *Daphnia magna*

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The rise in the production and use of electrical and electronic products leads to the increase in usage of cadmium, increasing the risk of exposures to this metal and justifying its inclusion in the list of restricted hazardous substances by the European Union. Despite the plethora of studies available, the full toxicity spectrum and the mechanisms behind cadmium toxicity in aquatic biota still need further clarification. The present study contributes to such clarification, by characterizing the sub-lethal effects of an exposure (7 days) to the EC20 concentration of cadmium (4.527 µg L⁻¹) in the freshwater keystone species *Daphnia magna*. A holistic approach across multiple levels of biological organization was applied, starting at a molecular level with epigenetic endpoints (total 5-mC DNA methylation and total DNA methyltransferases activity) and transcriptomic analysis (RNA-Seq), then working up to higher levels of biological organization by evaluating phenotypic effects at the sub-cellular and individual level. Exposure to cadmium caused global genome hypomethylation and altered activity of DNA methylation related enzymes. These changes in the epigenome were accompanied by significant gene transcription modulation, with 253 up- and 157 down-regulated genes, some of them in biological processes and pathways that correlate with the responses found for phenotypic endpoints. A significant increase of antioxidant enzymes, lipid peroxidation levels and DNA damage was recorded, alongside a reduction on physiological functions and somatic growth in exposed organisms. These findings provide insights into cadmium adverse outcome pathways considering DNA methylation as molecular initiating events. CESAM was funded by FCT/MCTES (UIDP/50017/2020 + UIDB/50017/2020 + LA/P/0094/2020) through national funds; project EPIBOOST, funded by the European Union (Grant 101078991; DOI:

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1.01.T-05 Beyond Exposure: Investigating the Transgenerational Effects of Bisphenol S in Zebrafish

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Bisphenol S (BPS), a commonly used substitute for Bisphenol A (BPA), has been detected in surface waters at increasing concentrations (from ng/L to low µg/L), primarily due to its widespread industrial applications, especially in the production of polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins. As current knowledge regarding the toxicity of BPS in non-target organisms is limited, therefore, this study aims to evaluate the ecological risks of BPS in aquatic ecosystems through a transgenerational bioassay with *Danio rerio* (zebrafish) as a model organism. The first generation (F0) was exposed to environmentally relevant concentrations of BPS (0.4, 2, and 10 µg/L direct exposure) and subsequent generations, F1 and F2, were grown in clean water (intergenerational and transgenerational, respectively). We characterized physiological, biochemical and molecular responses to disclose cause-effects relationships and contribute to the understanding of the underlying mechanisms behind the adverse physiological responses. In F0, a significant decrease in the fertilization rate was observed and several biochemical biomarkers (i.e. catalase, glutathione S-transferase and acetylcholinesterase) were altered by the lowest and highest concentrations, in both males and females brains. Parental BPS exposure altered several endpoints in non-directly exposed zebrafish (F1 and F2), by affecting their growth, heart rate, behaviour and other physiological parameters such as Fulton's condition factor, gonadosomatic and hepatosomatic indexes. To better understand the observed effects described so far, we began by performing a transcriptomic analysis (RNA-seq) on F1 embryos at 24 hpf. F1 embryos descendant from parental exposure to 0.4 µg/L of BPS, were the ones that revealed the largest number of altered genes compared to the control group. The majority of those were downregulated and 8 KEGG pathways were affected, such as oxidative phosphorylation, RNA degradation, ribosome, cardiac muscle contraction and PPAR signalling pathway. Results so far suggest that BPS, at environmentally relevant concentrations, was capable of inducing several direct, inter and transgenerational effects in different biological processes in zebrafish. Therefore, with this conceptual approach, we also hope to promote the assessment of the environmental hazards and risks of this compound. This study is supported by the project TRANSEPIC (2022.02922.PTDC, doi: 10.54499/2022.02925.CEECIND/CP1728/CT0004) and the author Marta Ribeiro acknowledges the Portuguese Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia for her PhD grant (2022.12763.BD)

1.01.P Unveiling Long-Term Ecological Impacts: From Epigenetic Biomarkers to Multigenerational and Chronic Effects of Environmental Contaminants Including Their Mixtures

1.01.P-Tu001 Sub-lethal Effects of Cadmium and Ciprofloxacin in Freshwater Green Microalgae: Epigenetic and Phenotypic Responses

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Anthropogenic activities often lead to contamination of waters with harmful substances such as metals, pharmaceuticals and other exogenous chemicals. As epigenetic mechanisms shape gene-environment interactions, the study of the epigenetic alterations in these organisms can provide clues to better understand how they face environmental challenges and how to protect them. Assuming the importance of microalgae as producers in freshwater food chains, we assessed the effects in *Parachlorella* sp. of exposure (10 days) to sublethal levels of cadmium, a legacy environmental contaminant, and ciprofloxacin, an antibiotic that has been recognised as an emerging contaminant in freshwater (yield EC20 after testing according to the OECD guideline no. 201; 90.3 µg Cd/L and 7.68 mg ciprofloxacin/L). We comparatively followed total DNA methylation and several phenotypic endpoints, namely DNA damage (comet assay), physiological (growth, efficiency of photosystem II and oxygen production were assessed) and biochemical biomarkers (oxidative stress and damage). Cadmium tended to induce hypomethylation and ciprofloxacin hypermethylation of the microalgae genome. Both chemicals induced a slight decrease in biomass yield but there were no effects or slight stimulation in photosystem II efficiency and oxygen

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Sources of cadmium

Cadmium in freshwater ecosystems

Cadmium (Cd) is a global freshwater contaminant

Higher Cd usage increases Cd occurrence in freshwaters

Cd is usually found in nature at concentrations below $1.25 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$

Cd full toxicity spectrum towards aquatic biota is unknown

Characterize the effects of an environmentally-plausible Cd exposure in *Daphnia magna*, linking molecular responses to downstream phenotypic effects

1

Acute immobilization test (OECD Test No. 202)

➤ 48h immobilization data used to calculate the EC₂₀ through Probit analysis

➤ **EC₂₀ = 4.527 (1.718 – 7.790) µg L⁻¹**

2

Final exposure design

Control

**Exposed
(EC₂₀)**

16 h light / 8 h dark

20° C

- Exposed from birth to 7 days-old with food supply
- 5 biological replicates

**Environmental
relevance**

Cd concentrations found in a contaminated European freshwater system

Up to **37 µg L⁻¹** (Bervoets et. al, 2009)

3 Endpoints analyzed

➤ **Epigenetic biomarkers**
Total DNA methylation (5-mC) levels & Total DNA methyltransferases activity (ELISA kits)

➤ **Gene expression analysis**
RNA-Seq & Differential gene expression analysis (GO and KEGG enrichment analysis)

➤ **Biochemical biomarkers**
Antioxidant enzymes activity and lipid peroxidation levels

➤ **Genotoxicity biomarker**
DNA damage levels (Alkaline comet assay)

➤ **Physiological biomarkers**
Post-exposure heart rate & somatic growth determination

Levels of biological organization

Results & Discussion

Molecular level - Epigenome

➤ Cd exposure alters the epigenetic landscape

“Writer” enzymes ?

Results & Discussion

Molecular level - Epigenome

➤ Cd exposure alters the epigenetic landscape

“Eraser” enzymes?
Passive DNA
TET demethylation

Causes

Effects

Total DNA methylation

DNMTs activity

Reduced SAM availability

Decreased ability of DNA to function as a substrate to DNMTs

Results & Discussion

Molecular level - Transcriptome

➤ Cd-induced DNA methylation changes probably elicit an altered gene expression profile

Gene expression trend

Metal ion metabolism / Cellular homeostasis

Cell signaling

Amino acids metabolism

Enriched KEGG Pathways

Results & Discussion

(Sub)cellular level

Transcriptomic response

- Genes involved in the cytochrome P450 and glutathione antioxidant pathways **up-regulated**

Antioxidant enzymes activity

- Genes involved in metal metabolism **down-regulated**

Lipid peroxidation

Oxidation

DNA damage

- Gene involved in DNA repair **down-regulated**

IBRv2 index

Ferritin heavy chain - LFC = -11.44
DBH-like monooxygenase protein 2 - LFC = -10.71

REV1 - LFC = -7.65

- Cd exposure disrupts other metals metabolism and leads to cell death via ferroptosis (Hong et al., 2022)
- *REV1* loss leads to higher susceptibility to DNA damage (Agyare-Tabbi et al., 2024)

Results & Discussion

Organism level

Transcriptomic response

- Genes involved in calcium homeostasis **down-regulated**

- Genes involved in **digestive function** and **exoskeleton structure** **down-regulated**

- *D. magna* heart rate is regulated by intracellular calcium levels and is a good indicator of daphnids fitness (Pirtle et al., 2018)
- Cd-exposed *D. magna* allocate energy towards detoxification and survival and away from growth and reproduction (Knops et al., 2001)

Main conclusions

The obtained results underpin Cd **sub-lethal exposures** as a significant challenge to *D. magna* thriving

This work provides insights into Cd prolific mechanisms of toxic action considering **DNA methylation as a molecular initiating event**

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Thank you for your attention